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Research Article

**C-MAC VIDEO LARYNGOSCOPE PROGRESSES LARYNGOSCOPE
ASSESSMENT IN MALLAMPATI SESSION 2 ALSO 3 CASES**¹Dr Muhammad Arsalan Saleem, ²Dr Muhammad Omer, ³Dr Haroon Rasheed¹Casualty Medical Officer in DHQ, DI Khan, ²BHU, Bolianwal Attock, ³Hazrat Barri Sarkar (HBS) College and Hospital.

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Abstract:

Objective: Researchers expected to consider C-MAC video laryngoscope (VLC) through Macintosh laryngoscope through regards to laryngoscope see, necessity for outside laryngeal control, essential of aeronautics course assistant's comparable stylet, time essential to comprehend tracheal intubation also hemodynamic variations in Mallampati session two in addition three cases.

Methodology: The current research was led at Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore Pakistan from July 2017 to September 2018. Seventy sufferers who had been yielded for elective cautious treatment necessitating conventional amnesia through endotracheal intubation remained indiscriminately assigned to ensue by endotracheal intubation use of ordinary Macintosh laryngoscope (Set-A) or else C-MAC VLC (Set-B). Subsequent the standardized overall narcotic show, period for intubation, laryngoscope see, prerequisite for outside control, also hemodynamic limitations all through also after intubation had been enrolled throughout find a few solutions concerning period.

Results: It used to be discovered that C-MAC VLC improves laryngoscope see in surveyed extraordinary flying course setting, and thusly decreases necessity for outside laryngeal control and usage of stylet. Never less, hemodynamic weight reply remained expansive through C-MAC VLC than Macintosh laryngoscopy. Here remained colossal refund in period occupied for intubation through conservative Macintosh laryngoscope once on or hand through C-MAC® VLC. Center all out intubation time for Macintosh and C-MAC® VLC were 24.9 and 36.34 sec independently ($p = 0.001$).

Conclusion: C-MAC video laryngoscope propels laryngoscope evaluation in jumbled course condition identified with obvious Macintosh laryngoscope, yet n again at cost of postponed time held for intubation besides expanded hemodynamic misgiving answer. Colossal measure examines may continue being fundamental to change conceivable achievement of intubation through cutting-edge novel instrument.

Keywords: Video laryngoscope, Laryngoscopy, Intubation, Anxiety reply, Hemodynamic, Airway Administration/arrangement, Glottis, Intubation, Intratracheal/arrangement; Laryngoscopy/ arrangement.

Corresponding author:

Dr. Muhammad Arsalan Saleem,
Casualty Medical Officer in DHQ, DI Khan

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Endotracheal intubation has converted into a normal bit of passing on an accepted ache relieving. Laryngoscopy is commonly achieved to assist intubation as a bit of regularly occurring amnesia [1]. Macintosh laryngoscope remains maximum for most part used system to truly image constructions of larynx and alongside se traces energize endotracheal intubation [2]. In any case, its supportiveness when in doubt of irksome avionics path famous to be limited. Scarcely any examinations have prescribed that usage of video laryngoscope (VLS) may want to enhance point of view on larynx and encourages intubation in tricky flight route conditions. C-MAC® VLS sharp edge is organized like Macintosh, with a greater perfect role of a camcorder at distal end of edge [3]. It may be used like Macintosh for straight laryngoscopy in addition for underhanded laryngoscopy once supervisor sees larynx on video screen. Circuitous laryngoscope see on video display screen permits companion to realize consequence of slightly exterior laryngeal manipulate on laryngoscope locate in circumstance of inconvenient intubation [4]. In any case, in any case, weight reply owing to laryngoscopy also tracheal intubation have an impact on cardiac limitations also intracranial mass. Cause of this examination used to be to consider glottic see, want of streamlining move, necessity for aeronautics direction subordinate, period taken for intubation also hemodynamic answer among Macintosh laryngoscope in addition C-MAC® VLS in midst of endotracheal intubation in Mallampati category two in addition three cases [5].

METHODOLOGY:

Afterwards assist from local Research Morals Board, seventy participants by Mallampati Classification 2 and 3 having a spot with ASA grade 1 and 2, encountering elective medicinal machine underneath established amnesia with endotracheal intubation in Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore Pakistan, from July 2017 to September 2018, had been chosen. Throughout preoperative valuation, people remained assumed the patient records piece also period to look at cloth also slightly inquiries about examination have been answered. Sufferers remained arranged prostrate through if head also neck at perfect function for intubation. Preceding to choose of amnesia, one of three laryngoscopes, both C-MAC® or Macintosh, was picked discretionarily through way of PC made subjective number. A comparative nastiest performed out all intubations in examination gearing. C-MAC® gauge 5 and Macintosh measure 5 edges were picked for all patients in examination. During decision and all thru framework, oxygen drenching, give up tidal CO₂,

non-meddlesome heartbeat and heartbeat have been watched. records amassed included Cormack-Leanne diagram of laryngoscope see, imperative of streamlining move, prerequisite for aeronautics direction subordinate (if Cormack-Leanne grade was once more than 3b), period occupied for intubation in addition hemodynamic reply amongst Macintosh laryngoscope also C-MAC® VLS in midst of endotracheal intubation in working room. Intubation period used to be described as between time from consideration of laryngoscope sharp area into mouth to swelling of tracheal barrel sleeve. Succeeding tracheal intubation, right function of tracheal chamber remained once avowed via auscultation in addition capnography. Uncertainty danger to compelling intubation outperformed 180 sec, venture remained considered as a failure and qualified for shirking from examination. avionics course was n supervised as shown via ASA irksome flying course computation and standards. outcomes have been conveyed in strategies and degrees. differentiations between two get-towers were taken a gander at usage of Chi-square test, also ANOVA. P value>0.06 stayed measured as antically basic.

RESULTS:

Estimation elements had been consistently appropriated between two events (Table 1). intubation time, laryngoscope see, and greater strikes compulsory, stylet exercised remain illustrated (Table 2). hemodynamic replies to intubation among together get-togethers at preop, 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6 minutes are regarded Table 3 core intubation period for C-MAC® and Macintosh have been 36.34 and 24.9 sec (p = 0.001). The capability of extra than 6 sec to intubate between get-togethers was once viewed clinically gigantic. re have been no colossal partitions in laryngoscope see or greater strikes required. Irregular laryngoscopy through C-MAC® conveyed Cormack-Leanne grade 1/3a/3b/4a/4b/5 finds in 0/22/8/0/0/1 seeing unreservedly, n once more shut assessments had been uncovered in 0/21/9/1/0/0 cases with straight laryngoscopy through Macintosh freely. Mallampati rankings have been thusly appropriated between 2 social gatherings. In C-MAC gutting, 10 victims required outdoor laryngeal manage (BURP move), 3 patients required use of stiletto invigorate tracheal intubation. In Macintosh pack 12 victims essential BURP, 7 respondents' essential utilization of stylet to allow tracheal intubation. That is, out of 10 victims in C-MAC collectively and eleven sufferers in Macintosh glaring, who required BURP, three in C-MAC Group (p regard 0.0828) and 7 in Macintosh Group (p regard 0.00036) essential Stylet for intubation. The current fundamental for stylet used to

be quantifiably massive in Macintosh adjusting, nonexclusive accomplishment charge of tracheal intubation used to be at one time a hundred percent in two social gatherings. hemodynamic weight response to laryngoscopy (Table 3, Figure 1 and 2) was once substantial in C-MAC pack at 1, 2-and 3-min between

times, possibly in context on surrendered timespan of laryngoscopy. An improvement in beat of over 21% and suggest vein weight of more than 12 mmHg between social things to do used to be considered clinically huge.

Table 1: Participant demographics

Demographic Information	Macintosh	C-MAC
average age (years)	22:8	20:10
Gender (man: woman)	20:10	18:12
Average Body Mass Index (kg/m ²)	38.03	41.03
Mallampati 2:3	25.3	25.8

Table 2: Intubation period, Rating of Laryngoscopy, Obligation of ELM, Requirement for Stylet, Accomplishment frequency:

Intubation	Macintosh	C-MAC	p-value
Intubation Period (sec)	24.9	36.34	0.001
Laryngoscope view (Session 1/2a/2b/3a/3b/4)	0/21/9/0/0/0	0/20/9/1/0/0	1.598
Exterior Laryngeal Manipulation (n)	6	2	1.254
Want for stylet (n)	10	9	1.681
Victory amount (%)	100%	100%	NS

Table 3: Assessment of Heart Rate also Average Arterial Pressure

Parameter	Set A N=32 Mean+SD	Set B N=32 Mean+SD	P-Value
Preop HR	104.47 ± 2.68	110.17 ± 4.17	.01
Preop MAP	77.60 ± 4.64	78.07 ± 4.01	.68
HR-Zero	89.50 ± 2.86	90.50 ± 3.60	.24
MAP-Zero	101.63 ± 3.49	118.00 ± 5.09	.02
HR-1	110.03 ± 3.19	117.60 ± 4.12	.02
MAP-1	126.60 ± 5.08	110.07 ± 3.93	.03
HR-2	90.03 ± 3.34	90.43 ± 1.99	.58
AP-2	95.80 ± 3.41	110.97 ± 3.24	.03
HR-3	104.13 ± 3.79	99.07 ± 2.95	.02
MAP-3	80.50 ± 3.43	76.07 ± 3.28	.29
HR-5	94.67 ± 1.81	97.90 ± 1.77	.24
MAP-5	88.80 ± 1.45	90.83 ± 1.80	.18

DISCUSSION:

Our effects exhibited a little anyway quantifiably primary alteration in average intubation period among C-MAC® also Macintosh laryngoscopes. C-MAC® also Macintosh bleeding edges are undefined in format also capacities secured use of one contraption be transferable to following gadget when C-MAC® remains exercised as quick laryngoscope [6]. In expected irksome avionics course, C-MAC® VLS has

better execution to extent shorter intubation time, greater accomplishment rate and much fewer enhancing moves. Disregarding way that VLSs supply a tolerable point of view on larynx, y may no longer assurance a fundamental tracheal intubation, and may also draw out time required for productive intubation [7]. Thusly, we differentiated show of C-MAC® and Macintosh in sufferers through the foreseen challenging flying direction concerning laryngoscope

see, necessity for streamlining moves, crucial of stylet, period occupied for intubation also hemodynamic adjustments at 2,3,4,5,6 min intervals [8]. Starting late exhibited C-MAC® D-sharp area (irksome aeronautics direction edge) has been regarded to improve accomplishment fee of endotracheal intubation in patients with predicted inconvenient flying course. Patients from two social events had no simple complexities. Oxygenation used to be all round kept up despite assortment in intubation times on account of strategy of preoxygenation that used to be coordinated in our examination [9]. re are a few necessities that can be perceived in our examination. Directly off bat, it is stupid to hope to astonish inspector about contraption being practiced. Our current examination stayed completed on ASA 1 and 2 no hypertensive sufferers sent for optionally available parietic systems. Result can also go in tragedies or else in hypertensive sufferers or else if case remains with or challenging avionics route markers [10].

CONCLUSION:

We endorse that C-MAC video laryngoscope recovers laryngoscope see in Mallampati session 3 and 4 flight course observes and lessens requirement for exterior laryngeal control in addition stylet. The period occupied for intubation remains lengthier through C-MAC® video laryngoscope than standard Macintosh laryngoscope. C-MAC® video laryngoscope improves laryngoscope find in testing flight course settings, nerveless, broad research is required to choose last accomplishment of intubation.

REFERENCES:

1. Boker AM. Use of Airtraq, C-Mac, and Glidescope laryngoscope is better than Macintosh in novice medical students' hands: A manikin study. 2011;5(4):376- 381. [Free full text]
2. Shahir h, M akbar, Joanna SM. Comparison between C-mac® video-laryngoscope and

- macintosh direct laryngoscope during Cervical spine immobilization. M.E.J. Anesth. 2015;23(1):43-50.
3. Cormack RS, Lehane J .Difficult tracheal intubation in obstetrics. Anaesthesia 1984 Nov;39(11):1105-1111. [PubMed]
4. Cavus E, Kieckhafer J, Doerges V, Moeller T, Thee C, Wagner K. The C-MAC videolaryngoscope: first experiences with a new device for videolaryngoscopy guided intubation. Anesth Analg. 2010 Feb;110(2):473- 477. [PubMed]
5. Jungbauer A, Schumann M, Bunkhorst V, Börgers A, Groeben H. Expected difficult tracheal intubation: a prospective comparison of direct laryngoscopy and video laryngoscopy in 200 patients.
6. Miller RD, Pardo M. Airway management of Anesthesia. Basics of anesthesia 2005;6:1636
7. Kaur S, Gupta A, Ranjana, Rita. Intubating conditions and stress response to laryngoscopy: Comparison between Macintosh and levering (McCoy's Type) Laryngoscope. J Anaesthesiol Clin Pharmacol. 2009;25(3):333-336.
8. Kaplan MB, Hagberg CA, Ward DS, Brambrink A, Chhibber AK, Heidegger T, et al. Comparison of direct and video assisted views of the larynx during routine intubation. J Clin Anesth. 2006;18(5):357-62. [PubMed]
9. Enomoto Y, Asai T, Arai T, Kamishima K, Okuda Y. Pentax-AWS, a new videolaryngoscope is more effective than the Macintosh laryngoscope for tracheal intubation in patients with restricted neck movements: a randomised comparative study. Br J Anaesth. 2008 Apr;100(4):544-8. [PubMed] [Free full text]
10. Cooper RM, Pacey JA, Bishop MY, McCluskey SA. Early clinical experience with a new videolaryngoscope (Glidescope) in 728 patients. Can J Anaesth. 2005 Feb;52(2):191-8.